

ARTICLE

Methods, Tools, and Technologies

Statistical assessment on determining local presence of rare bat species

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Abstract

Surveying cryptic, sparsely distributed taxa using autonomous recording units, although cost-effective, provides imperfect knowledge about species presence. Summertime bat acoustic surveys in North America exemplify the challenges with characterizing sources of uncertainty: observation error, inability to census populations, and natural stochastic variation. Statistical uncertainty, if not considered thoroughly, hampers determining rare species presence accurately and/or estimating rangewide status and trends with suitable precision. Bat acoustic data are processed using an automated workflow in which proprietary or open-source algorithms assign a species label to each recorded high-frequency echolocation sequence. A false-negative occurs, if a species is actually present but not recorded and/or all recordings from the species are of such poor quality that a correct species identity cannot be assigned to any observation. False positives for a focal species are a direct result of the presence and incorrect identification of a recording from another species. We compare four analytical approaches in terms of parameter estimation and their resulting (in)correct decisions regarding species presence or absence using realistic data-generating scenarios for bat acoustic data within a simulation study. The current standard for deciding species presence or absence uses a multinomial likelihood-ratio test p value (maximum likelihood estimate [MLE]-metric) that accounts for known species misidentifications, but not imperfect detection and only returns a binary outcome (evidence of presence or not). We found that the MLE-metric had estimated median correct decisions less than 60% for presence and greater than 85% for absence. Alternatively, a multispecies count detection model was equivalent to or better than the MLE-metric for correct claims of rare species presence or absence using the posterior probability a species was present at a site and, importantly, provided unbiased estimates of relative activity and probability of occurrence, creating opportunities for reducing posterior uncertainty through the inclusion of meaningful covariates. Single-species occupancy models with and without false-positive detections removed

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were insufficient for determining local presence because of substantially biased occurrence and detection probabilities. We propose solutions to potential barriers for integrating local, short-term and rangewide, long-term acoustic surveys within a cohesive statistical framework that facilitates determining local species presence with uncertainty concurrent with estimating species–environment relationships.

KEYWORDS

acoustic survey, autonomous recording units, Bayesian hierarchical model, count detection model, false positives, imperfect detection, North American Bat Monitoring Program, occupancy modeling, sampling design

INTRODUCTION

Decision-making in the face of uncertainty is a fundamental challenge for natural resource managers (Polasky et al., 2011). Recommendations related to a species conservation status under the US Endangered Species Act (ESA 1973, as amended) are typically assessed at a rangewide extent using long-term monitoring datasets, when possible (e.g., Smith et al., 2018). Status assessments consider a species' persistence on the landscape under plausible scenarios for future conditions related to their known stressors (e.g., in the case of bats, impacts of climate change, energy development, forest management, and disease; Frick et al., 2020; Hoyt et al., 2021). Ideally, spatially extensive and longitudinal datasets are collated to fuel statistical models for estimating with uncertainty whether populations are increasing, decreasing, or stable over time under hypothetical scenarios (Cheng et al., 2021; Erickson et al., 2014). Once a species is deemed “threatened or endangered” under ESA, approval for a habitat alteration often requires a determination of species presence or absence within a potentially affected area to minimize possible “take” of vulnerable species (USFWS, 2020). Data collection to inform the permitting process, typically, relies on surveys over a shorter time period within a given project area (e.g., for *Myotis sodalis* and *M. septentrionalis*; see USFWS, 2020). Our work is motivated by considering whether a common statistical inference framework is available for addressing both rangewide status assessments and local decisions regarding rare bat species presence using data collected by autonomous recording units (ARUs)—acoustic surveys.

The observational unit for bat acoustic surveys is a high-frequency recording that can be visualized using a spectrogram (Aodha et al., 2018). Many species can be recorded during a nightly interval at a specific deployment location (a “visit”). A nuance of bat acoustic data is that the sheer volume of echolocation sequences recorded during a visit necessitates an automated workflow for managing the recordings (Aodha et al., 2018). Recordings are processed using proprietary classification software or open-source machine-learning

algorithms to assign or label an echolocation sequence to a particular species (Acevedo et al., 2009; Sugai et al., 2018). Consequently, cross-species misidentifications—the wrong species is assigned to a recording—can be introduced during the automated classification process. Misclassifications at the recording level, if not accounted for, can propagate into visit-level false-positive and false-negative detections that can bias resulting statistical inferences (Banner et al., 2018; Chambert, Waddle, et al., 2018; Clement et al., 2014).

To minimize the potential for a software program to “confuse” echolocation sequences among bats in the genus *Myotis* and *Lasiurus borealis*, the “maximum-likelihood” metric was developed based on misclassification rates calculated from high-frequency recordings with known species identities (the “maximum likelihood estimate [MLE]”-metric; Britzke et al., 2002). The MLE-metric is the current standard supported by the US Fish and Wildlife Service (USFWS) for determining local presence for two rare bat species, *M. septentrionalis* and *M. sodalis*. To ensure consistency in application among project areas, the USFWS independently approves automated bat acoustic identification software programs (i.e., autotransformer) for acoustic survey work (USFWS, 2020). The MLE-metric returned by approved software is then used to make a decision about species presence at a site. For regulatory purposes, the USFWS considers *M. septentrionalis* and *M. sodalis* present at a local site, if one or more survey nights (visits) return an MLE-metric less than 0.05. To date, no work has explored the performance of the MLE-metric for determining local bat presence using a statistical simulation study. The benefit of our simulation investigation is that the true state (species present or not) is known and available for investigating how often the MLE-metric approach arrives at a correct decision under different data-generating scenarios for bat acoustic data.

We consider whether Bayesian occupancy models are a viable alternative to the MLE-metric for determining local presence of rare bat species within the same simulation study. Often, biologists summarize the nightly recordings to detection/nondetection (one or zero) for a single focal species and apply occupancy models for statistical analyses

(Rodhouse et al., 2012). Standard occupancy models account for imperfect detection (MacKenzie et al., 2002) at the visit level, which, for bat ARU data, arise because a species is actually present but not recorded, and/or all recordings from the species are of such poor quality that a correct species identity cannot be assigned to any observation (Banner et al., 2018). A visit-level false-positive detection is the consequence of the autoclassifier incorrectly assigning the focal species label to at least one recording. To proceed with standard occupancy modeling, one option is to effectively override or remove false-positive detections prior to statistical analyses (Barré et al., 2019). Currently, for North American bats, false-positive detections are removed either by the “MLE-metric” from the computer software at a nightly level (visit level) (e.g., Nocera et al., 2019b; Rojas et al., 2018) or by way of human vetters that are considered “experts” (Banner et al., 2018; Rojas et al., 2018). The human vetters follow a regional “key” or established rule set to confirm at least 1–5 recordings are assigned the correct species label (e.g., Reichert et al., 2018). Occupancy modeling provides explanatory inferences about species probability of occurrence and how those may relate to environmental gradients, such as elevation, percent forest, and terrain ruggedness (e.g., Wright et al., 2021). However, summarizing ARU data to a binary response may lack the resolution required for detecting more subtle population impacts from disease or disturbances (e.g., fire), creating temporally nonanalog conditions that are spatially heterogeneous across a landscape (e.g., Hyzy et al., 2020; Law et al., 2018; Nocera et al., 2019a).

Recently, a Bayesian hierarchical model was developed for ARU data that provides estimates of species-specific activity at a local deployment location and estimates of site-level species occurrence associations with uncertainty (Stratton et al., 2022; Wright et al., 2020). The multispecies count detection model by Wright et al. (2020) utilizes the count of detections per species and avoids reducing the data to simply detection/nondetection for a nightly recording interval. The multispecies count detection model provides a potential bridge between two important objectives—broad-scale status and trends *and* local-scale decision-making. In fact, we show the mathematical connection between the MLE-metric calculation (Britzke et al., 2002) and a posterior probability from the multispecies count detection model that allows for a direct comparison of these two methods for local-scale decision-making (full details in Appendix S1). The key distinction between these approaches is that the count detection model allows for imperfect detection and inclusion of habitat and environmental conditions that inform and have the potential to improve the determination of local presence for rare species.

We conduct a simulation-based assessment to compare the current USFWS regulatory standard of using the MLE-metric for determining species presence at a site to the

multispecies count detection model and two alternative implementations of single-species occupancy models. We focus on the relative performance of the analytical approaches in terms of making a correct decision regarding species presence or absence at a specific location. A concern when relying on statistical estimation for making a decision is whether the fitted models recover the data-generating values with reasonable accuracy and precision; if not, the ability to make a correct decision may be affected. Therefore, we include an investigation into parameter estimation for the Bayesian modeling approaches to verify whether they are statistically sound alternatives for application in local decision-making. Our work is motivated by our belief there is an unrealized opportunity in North American bat conservation to inform both site-level decisions about rare species presence and estimate species occurrence and relative activity related to environmental conditions using a unified statistical design and modeling framework.

METHODS

In *Summer acoustic bat survey guidelines*, we outline the two primary sampling designs used in North America for collecting summertime bat acoustic data. The guidance differs because the intended spatial scope of inference varied: a specific project area versus rangewide extents (denoted as goal of analysis in Figure 1). In “MLE”-metric calculation, we provide details on the current USFWS standard for determining local species presence based on the MLE-metric (denoted as gray pathway in Figure 1). Then, in *Bayesian models for bat acoustic data*, we outline three Bayesian model-based approaches for bat ARU data that we include because of their potential for estimating the probability a species occurs locally and throughout its range (denoted as black pathways in Figure 1). All the model-based options account for imperfect detection, but they differ in how species misclassifications are accounted for when estimating the probability of occurrence (see Figure 1). Finally in *Simulation study methods*, we describe our simulation study design for comparing the four analytical approaches in terms of their ability to assign the correct state of species (present or absent) at a site. The various factors we investigate were chosen because of their potential to influence estimating model parameters or assigning the (in)correct state of species presence or absence at a site (denoted by dashed ovals with call-out boxes in Figure 1).

Summer acoustic bat survey guidelines

In North America, state and federal regulations and policies require surveys to determine local presence of at least five bat species or subspecies (*Corynorhinus townsendii ingens*,

FIGURE 1 Conceptual diagram representing our simulation study comparing four analytical approaches for determining local presence of rare bat species. The black pathways denote Bayesian model-based approaches that allow for both explanatory modeling and local decisions regarding species presence. The gray arrows represent the fact using the MLE-metric at the site level (*MLESite*) to assess local species presence does not allow for estimating species–environment relationships more broadly (i.e., explanatory modeling). The stippled outlined boxes convey both the *Remove* and “*MLESite*” approaches rely on the MLE-metric calculation at the visit or site level to adjust for species misclassifications. Dashed circles represent nodes that were investigated in the simulation study with accompanying factors (in call-out boxes) that were varied either through the data-generating process (relative activity, occurrence probability, and autoclassifier accuracy rates), through design criteria (number of visits), or in the decision rule applied to assign species presence at a site (cutoff values).

C. t. virginianus, *Myotis grisescens*, *M. septentrionalis*, and *M. sodalis*) during the summer maternity season when most vulnerable to disturbance from management actions, for example, forest harvesting, prescribed burning, surface mining, and road construction and development (Silvis et al., 2016). Summer survey guidelines for determining sensitive species probable presence or absence to inform localized decisions are available from the USFWS (2020). Currently, USFWS guidelines are geared toward two particular at-risk species that hibernate during the winter and day roost in forests in the summer, *M. septentrionalis* and *M. sodalis*. Data are collected using stationary ARUs, but the spatial unit of a site is approximately 0.5 km² in an area or along a 1-km linear unit. Deployment periods vary by target species and location, but generally are 8–9 precipitation-free nights for an areal project and 2 nights/km for linear. Typically, these data are then analyzed using the MLE-metric at the visit level to make a decision regarding local species presence before obtaining project clearance (Figure 1, gray pathway).

Alternatively, an omnibus North American Bat Monitoring Program (NABat) designed to provide summertime status and trend estimation rangewide for multiple species simultaneously uses a common probabilistic master sample

design for site selection (Larsen et al., 2008). The master sample is based on a grid-based sampling frame with 10 × 10 km cells. Within each selected NABat grid cell, between 2 and 4 locations are selected for deploying ARUs for 1–4 nights (Loeb et al., 2015). The number of nights and locations within a grid cell can be informed by estimated species detection probabilities and field logistics (Rodriguez et al., 2019). NABat data have been analyzed at state-level (Neece et al., 2019), regional (Rodhouse et al., 2019), and rangewide (Udell et al., 2022) extents using various Bayesian hierarchical models. The inferential goals are typically to predict occurrence probabilities at all surveyed and nonsurveyed sites and also estimate species–environment relationships with uncertainty. We consider a subset of the available options for modeling bat acoustic data (described in *Bayesian models for bat acoustic data*) for our simulation investigation because they also afford a pathway to site-level decisions about presence (Figure 1, black pathways).

“MLE”-metric calculation

Britzke et al. (2002) introduced a MLE-metric for determining site-level species probable presence based on the

number of recordings labeled to a focal species by the autoclassifier (hereafter, “autoID”) during a given recording interval (e.g., one night or aggregated over many nightly surveys). The approach explicitly acknowledges that autoIDs are subject to false positives, and a false positive for one species is a direct result of the presence and incorrect identification of a recorded echolocation sequence from another species. Britzke et al. (2002) constructed a likelihood-ratio (LR) test for the null hypothesis of species absence as an approach to decide species presence after accounting for software inaccuracies.

Following Britzke et al. (2002),

$\phi_{kk'}$ = probability that a recording from species k' is identified to species k . For a community of K species, a matrix with dimensions $K \times K$ is defined, where each row represents the software autoID result, and each column is the true species identity;

θ_k^B = relative frequency of species k in sampled community, where we use the superscript B on the parameter to denote that it is from the Britzke et al. (2002) method;

N = total number of high-frequency sequences recorded and identified; and

n_k = the number of recordings identified to species k (autoIDs).

The classification probabilities ($\phi_{kk'}$) are assumed known and are based on a large set of voucher search-phase calls. From Britzke et al. (2002), “voucher calls were recorded from free flying bats in open areas with chemical light sticks on their backs such that the species emitting the echolocation call was known.” The relative frequency of a species in the sampled community (θ_k^B) is an unknown parameter. The MLE-metric assumes a multinomial data likelihood for the total number of identifiable recordings and the number of autoIDs per species (n_1, \dots, n_K) with probabilities $\sum_{k'=1}^K \phi_{kk'} \theta_{k'}^B$;

$$L(\mathbf{n}, \theta) \propto \prod_k \left(\sum_{k'=1}^K \phi_{kk'} \theta_{k'}^B \right)^{n_k}. \quad (1)$$

The MLE-metric is the p value from the LR test with null hypothesis that species k is absent from a site, $\theta_k^B = 0$ in Equation 1, versus the alternative hypothesis that the species is present, $\theta_k^B > 0$ in Equation 1. A p value provides evidence against the null hypothesis—the probability of observing a test statistic at least as extreme (or more extreme) as what was observed, assuming the null hypothesis (species absence) and assumptions listed in Appendix S1 are reasonable.

Although the USFWS *M. sodalis* protocol determines species probable presence or absence as the MLE-metric applied at a visit level (USFWS, 2020), we aggregated

counts of autoIDs over all nightly recording sessions at a deployment location to both increase the number of recordings (sample size) and perform an equivalent comparison with the model-based site-level decisions (denoted as “*MLESite*”; Appendix S1 and see *Assessing site-level decisions regarding species presence (absence)*). Current USFWS guidance suggests using a conservative 0.05 as the cutoff in the decision rule for determining localized presence (if MLE-metric $p < 0.05$, claim species present; USFWS, 2020). Hereafter, we denote the *MLESite* threshold value as α because it represents the significance level chosen for the hypothesis test (see Figure 1).

Bayesian models for bat acoustic data

We explored three Bayesian modeling options for bat acoustic surveys (denoted by rounded rectangles in Figure 1): (1) a standard single-species occupancy model that accounts for imperfect detection (denoted as “*Naive*”); (2) a single-species occupancy model with false-positive detections removed prior to analysis (denoted as “*Remove*”); and (3) a multispecies count detection model. The *Naive* and *Remove* approaches estimate probability of presence and detection for each species separately. Following notation from MacKenzie et al. (2002), let $i = \{1, \dots, n\}$ index sites and $j = \{1, \dots, J\}$ visits. Then, the partially observed state of a site, Z_i , is modeled as a Bernoulli random variable with probability ψ_i ($Z_i = 1$ if the focal species occurs at site i ; 0 otherwise). Presence (the Z state) is imperfectly observed. The probability the focal species is detected at a site in which it occurs is denoted by p . Thus, $Y_{ij}|Z_i = 1 \sim \text{Bernoulli}(p_{ij} \times z_i)$, where y_{ij} is 1 if the focal species is detected at site i during visit j and 0 otherwise. Because $y_{ij} = 1 \Rightarrow z_i = 1$, the single-species occupancy model assumes no false-positive detections are made at the visit level. Both the detection level and the occupancy level of the model can be extended to include covariates that explain heterogeneity in p and ψ among visits or among sites (MacKenzie et al., 2002).

The difference between the *Remove* and *Naive* approaches lies in the construction of the detection history matrices (MacKenzie et al., 2002). The detection history matrix is defined as the $n \times J$ matrix of the observed y_{ij} values for all (i, j) . The *Remove* approach preprocesses the autoID counts for each species prior to fitting a single-species occupancy model. The preprocess step is achieved by implementing the MLE-metric with $\alpha = 0.05$ based on the total number of identified recordings per species during a visit in an attempt to “*Remove*” false-positive errors prior to building the detection history matrix. The detection history matrix had a “1” entered for a visit, if the MLE-metric is < 0.05 ; otherwise, a “0” was entered. Alternatively, the *Naive* approach assumes that if at least one autoID is assigned to

the focal species during a visit, then that species was present during the visit (i.e., a “1” entry; otherwise a “0” entry). The *Naive* approach incorrectly assumes the software auto-classifier always assigns the correct species label to a recording.

The multispecies count detection model, a Bayesian hierarchical model, was developed for ARU data to account for the same properties noted by Britzke et al. (2002) that the rate of false positives for a species was related to both the autoclassification error rates and the presence and relative activity of other co-occurring bat species. In our application of the multispecies count detection model, we assume a two-species case (denoted as “2*SppCt*”). We assume the same information required for the MLE-metric is available for use in the 2*SppCt* model. Specifically, we assume that the accuracy rates from the classifiers are known and correct. Appendix S1 provides the mathematical connection between the *MLESite* approach and the posterior probability from the 2*SppCt*, which allows for a comparison of their (in)correct decisions about local presence within a simulation environment.

We briefly describe the multispecies count detection model, but see Wright et al. (2020) and Stratton et al. (2022) for additional guidance on data requirements and Bayesian prior specification when the classification probabilities are assumed unknown and estimated jointly. Following notation from Wright et al. (2020), let $i = \{1, \dots, n\}$ index sites, $j = \{1, \dots, J\}$ visits to each site within a season, and $k = \{1, \dots, K\}$ index possible species available for recording during a study. For site i , species k was present (1) or not (0) with probability ψ_{ik} and we model this latent presence state as

$$Z_{ik} \sim \text{Bernoulli}(\psi_{ik}), \quad (2)$$

and then, an appropriate link function (e.g., logit and probit) can be used to model site-level information to inform the probability a species occurred at a site ($Z_i = 1$) such as elevation or percentage forest cover. Given species k occurs at site i , the true number of echolocation sequences (recordings) for a species is modeled as

$$[Y_{ijk} | Z_{ik} = 1] \sim \text{Poisson}(\lambda_{ijk}), \quad (3)$$

where λ_{ijk} is the expected (mean) number of recordings per night, and $\log(\lambda_{ijk})$ can be used to include covariates associated with relative bat activity during a site-night visit, such as nightly minimum temperature or average wind speed. In the count detection model, the probability of a false negative (zero recorded and/or identifiable calls even though species present at site) is estimable as $\text{Pr}(Y_{ijk} = 0 | Z_{ik} = 1) = \exp(-\lambda_{ijk})$. The observed response data are the sum of autoIDs for each species (n_k)

and are modeled as Poisson counts as follows: $[n_k | Z, \lambda, \phi] = \text{Poisson}\left(\sum_{k'=1}^K Z_{ik'} \lambda_{ijk'} \phi_{kk'}\right)$.

Simulation study methods

For our study, we assumed only two species because our exploration utilized computer simulations and increasing to more species increased the computational demand. Our previous work verified that the multispecies count detection model returns unbiased parameter estimates when extended to bat assemblages composed of 10 species (Stratton et al., 2022). Similarly, other work has established the overestimation of occupancy probabilities when the *Naive* model is applied to datasets contaminated by false-positive detections from an omnibus source (Royle & Link, 2006), but we include it for completeness. The *Remove* approach has not been evaluated previously using a statistical simulation study, only with empirical observations of *M. septentrionalis* (Rojas et al., 2018).

Our first objective was to compare the three model-based approaches for estimating both the probability a species is detected (p) and the probability a species occurs (ψ). Our second objective was to compare the *MLESite* and suitable model-based approaches in terms of their application for discerning site-level species presence or absence correctly within the same simulation framework. Because we know that automatic classifiers for bat acoustic data are not 100% accurate, we generated datasets of autoIDs contaminated by recording or observation-level identification errors for two species (data were consistent with the 2*SppCt* model). The chosen parameter settings reflected our current understanding of two species (*M. lucifugus* and *M. sodalis*) that produce similar search-phase echolocation calls and tend to co-occur, and display considerable overlap in habitat association for many areas (Ford et al., 2005; Table 1). One species was assumed rare (e.g., *M. sodalis*) within a study area ($\psi_1 = 0.25$) and locally less active (relative activity rates averaging around one identifiable recording per night). The second species was assumed more widespread (e.g., *M. lucifugus*; $\psi_2 = 0.75$) and more active (relative activity rates with on average 10 identifiable recordings per night).

We considered five different simulation scenarios. Three scenarios reflected different (mis)classification probabilities with varying contributions of false-positive recordings from the common species (ϕ , Scenario 1, Scenario 2, and Scenario 3; Table 1). Scenario 1 assumed that the autoclassifier was 90% accurate for rare species recordings and only 65% accurate for a common species; consequently, the contribution of false positives from the common species was considerable at 35%. Scenario 2 assumed that the autoclassifier was only 65% accurate for rare species recordings, but the false-positive contributions from a common species were

TABLE 1 Parameter settings used to generate autoID datasets for 55 sites and 8 or 16 nightly surveys consistent with field knowledge and published work on *Myotis sodalis* (a rare species; denoted as “Spp 1”) and *M. lucifugus* (a common species; denoted as “Spp 2”)

Scenario	No. nights	No. sites	Species	ϕ_k	ψ_k	λ_k	p_k
1	8, 16	55	Spp 1	(0.90, 0.35)	0.25	0.3	0.26
			Spp 2	(0.10, 0.65)	0.75	10	0.999
2	8, 16	55	Spp 1	(0.65, 0.10)	0.25	0.3	0.26
			Spp 2	(0.35, 0.90)	0.75	10	0.999
3	8, 16	55	Spp 1	(0.65, 0.40)	0.25	0.3	0.26
			Spp 2	(0.35, 0.60)	0.75	10	0.999
4	8, 16	55	Spp 1	(0.90, 0.35)	0.50	0.3	0.26
			Spp 2	(0.10, 0.65)	0.75	10	0.999
5	8, 16	55	Spp 1	(0.90, 0.35)	0.25	0.7	0.50
			Spp 2	(0.10, 0.65)	0.75	10	0.999

Note: Simulated data assume the information about autoclassifier performance identifying species is correct and constant for all sites and revisits. ϕ_k has the columns as the true species identity and the rows refer to the autoID label. For example, under Scenario 1, autoID labels to species 1 are correctly assigned 90% of the time and are contaminated by false positives or incorrectly labeled as species 1 35% of the time, on average. ψ_k is the probability species k occurs at a site, λ_k is the relative activity rate for species k during a nightly survey, and p_k is the probability at least one call file is recorded for species k during a nightly survey.

lower with only 10% of recordings of the common species misidentified. Scenario 3 assumed the autoclassifier accuracy rate for both the rare and common species was low, respectively, 65% and 60%. The remaining two scenarios (Scenario 4 and Scenario 5) provided direct comparisons with Scenario 1; the classifier accuracy rates were assumed the same (ϕ equal for Scenario 1, Scenario 4, and Scenario 5 in Table 1). Scenario 4 assumed a higher occurrence probability for the rare species ($\psi_1 = 0.50$; Table 1). Scenario 5 assumed higher relative activity of the rare species, thereby increasing the expected number of recordings classified during a nightly interval.

All scenarios were assumed to have 55 sites with 8 or 16 recording nights per site for consistency with current guidelines from NABat and USFWS for the endangered *M. sodalis* and the *M. lucifugus*, a candidate for possible listing. We simulated 50 datasets under each scenario for both 8 and 16 visits, and applied all four analytical approaches to each dataset. Again, for the MLE-metric calculations and the *2SppCt*, we assumed that the autoclassifier (in)accuracy rates were known without error. The three model-based approaches were fit using NIMBLE (de Valpine et al., 2017, 2021). The different scenarios required different iterations, warm-up, and thinning of the MCMC to exhibit good mixing of the chains and evidence of convergence. Chains were visually assessed using trace plots, summarized with the Gelman-Rubin diagnostic (*Rhat*) and the number of effectively independent samples (n_{eff}) (*Rhat*, n_{eff} computed using *rstan*; Stan Development Team, 2020). Details for each scenario are provided in Appendix S2. We assumed diffuse priors of $[\psi_k] = \text{Uniform}(0, 1)$; $[p_k] = \text{Uniform}(0, 1)$; and a weakly informative prior of $[\lambda_k] = \text{Gamma}(\text{shape} = 2, \text{rate} = 0.25)$, which is right-skewed with the majority of the

mass between 0 and 20 and a mean of 8 (median 6.7) and represents a reasonable range of relative activity for the species we consider.

Parameter estimation

We compared estimated probability for rare species presence (ψ_1) and common species presence (ψ_2) among the *2SppCt*, *Remove*, and *Naive* approaches, as all three models provided Bayesian posterior distributions for these parameters. For visualization, we reported the average of the 2.5%, 50%, and 97.5% percentiles from the parameter posterior distributions over the 50 iterations of simulated data for all three models. We assessed estimation error (bias) and relative uncertainty conveyed by the 95% posterior intervals for all three models. Coverage was computed by calculating the proportion of simulated datasets that resulted in 95% posterior intervals including the true data-generating values. (Note: Slight deviations from nominal coverage are expected because of the small number [50] of simulated datasets for each scenario.) The *Remove* and *Naive* occupancy models provide an estimate of detectability (p_1 and p_2 for both species), whereas the *2SppCt* model provides an estimate of species-specific relative activity (λ_1 and λ_2).

Assessing site-level decisions regarding species presence (absence)

For each simulated dataset, we determined a site-level decision regarding a conclusion of species absent or

present with all four approaches (*MLESite*, *2SppCt*, *Remove*, and *Naive*) for comparison with the true known state of species absent ($Z = 0$) versus present ($Z = 1$). We summarized the number of sites with a specific decision conditional on the known true state of species presence or absence for each dataset comprised of 55 sites.

The *MLESite* approach used the total number of autoIDs classified to each species aggregated over the nightly surveys (8 or 16 visits) to arrive at a site-level decision of species presence or absence. The *MLESite* decision rule is based on a threshold that is related to a maximum tolerance for making a type I error (claiming species was present when actually absent). We explored different thresholds (α) for the decision rule embedded in the *MLESite* approach for concluding species presence (MLE-metric $< \alpha$) or absence (MLE-metric $\geq \alpha$). We considered $\alpha = 0.05, 0.1, 0.15,$ and 0.2 , which represents a reasonable range of tolerances for making type I errors (erroneously concluding species presence). These results are presented in Appendix S2.

The model-based approaches (*2SppCt*, *Remove*, and *Naive*) arrived at a site-level decision by using the Bayesian posterior probability a species occurs at a site. The model-based approaches used the posterior mean of the Z state for each site ($Pr[Z_i = 1|y]$) compared with a threshold (z_{cutoff}) to make a site-level decision about species presence or absence. The decision rule was defined as $Pr(Z_{ik} = 1|y) > z_{\text{cutoff}} \Rightarrow$ species k was claimed present at site i ; otherwise, species k was claimed absent at site i . We considered z_{cutoff} values of $0.05, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75,$ and 0.95 to represent a range of decision rules. Smaller z_{cutoff} values increased the number of sites with a decision of species present. Conversely, larger values of z_{cutoff} increased the number of sites with the state of species absent assigned. The threshold investigation results are presented in Appendix S2.

RESULTS

Generally, we found that changing the classifier accuracy from 0.90 to 0.65 and recording-level false-positive rate from 0.35 to 0.10 for the rare species did not impact *2SppCt* parameter estimation or the site-level decisions of *MLESite* and *2SppCt* because we assumed those values were known and correct (results in Appendix S2). The scenario where both species had poor autoclassifiers (true classification rates of 0.65 for rare species and 0.60 for common species in Scenario 3; Table 1) led to poor estimation of the relative activity using *2SppCt* across the 50 simulated datasets (Appendix S2). The unstable results suggest a minimum accuracy for species classification should be established, which was consistent with the

rigorous testing required by the USFWS to approve software for rare species surveys (USFWS and USGS, 2019).

We include all results for the common, easily detected species in Appendix S2. The results showed little variability among scenarios and near-perfect correct site-level decisions among the five data-generating scenarios we investigated. This is not very surprising because site-level decisions about species presence are robust when a species has very high probability of being detected acoustically, when present. The contributions of recording-level false positives from the rare species were too infrequent relative to the number of correct identifications of the common species to bias the decision outcome. The utility of including the “common” species, statistically, is as the source of recording-level false positives for the rare species.

In the following sections, we explore parameter estimation for the model-based approaches and then compare *MLESite* approach with suitable model-based approaches for determining whether the rare species was present at a site. We assume the classifier was 90% accurate identifying the rare species with a substantial source of false positives contributed by the common species recordings (35%). We focus on comparing three scenarios to investigate whether increasing the occurrence probability for the rare species from $\psi_1 = 0.25$ to $\psi_1 = 0.5$ (denoted as $[\psi = 0.25, \lambda = 0.3]$ vs. $[\psi = 0.5, \lambda = 0.3]$) or increasing the detection probability for the rare species from $p_1 = 0.25$ to $p_1 = 0.5$ (denoted as $[\psi = 0.25, \lambda = 0.3]$ vs. $[\psi = 0.25, \lambda = 0.7]$) influenced model parameter estimates or site-level decisions.

Naive, Remove, and 2SppCt model estimation for rare species occurrence and detection probabilities

The count detection model is the most realistic data-generating model for bat acoustic data currently in the literature, and given that simulated datasets were generated under this model, it was not surprising that the *2SppCt* version consistently returned unbiased ψ estimates for the rare species (Figure 2, top row, with additional results in Appendix S2: Figures S1 and S2). The posterior estimates for relative activity or the average number of recordings per species were unbiased, and 95% coverage was achieved for most scenarios, as expected (Figure 2, bottom row and Appendix S2: Figures S1 and S2). There was a slight reduction in uncertainty (narrower posterior intervals) for the rare species with 16 rather than 8 visits (Appendix S2: Figures S1 and S2).

The *Remove* approach overestimated the probability of presence (Figure 2, top row) and underestimated the probability of detection regardless of the assumed average occurrence or relative activity (Figure 2, middle row). The

FIGURE 2 Comparison of average (thick line) and individual (thin lines) 95% posterior intervals from fitting Bayesian-model-based approaches (*2SppCt*, *Remove*, or *Naive*). Rare species estimated probability of presence (ψ , top row), probability of detection (p , middle row), and relative activity (λ , bottom row) based on 16 visits and 55 sites under three different data-generating scenarios (corresponding column labels [$\psi = 0.25, \lambda = 0.3$], [$\psi = 0.50, \lambda = 0.3$], or [$\psi = 0.25, \lambda = 0.7$]). Horizontal black lines reflect the parameter values used for generating the datasets. Coverage of the data-generating parameter values is indicated by the interval color (red = poor, purple = decent). There were a few iterations of the simulation that resulted in MCMC samplers that did not converge (Rhat > 1.1) for the *2SppCt* model, and these iterations were excluded before average posterior intervals were computed. Additional convergence details and scenarios are included in Appendix S2: Figures S1 and S2.

small detection probabilities explain the larger uncertainty for occurrence probabilities using *Remove* (Figure 2). The posterior intervals based on the *Remove* approach were more noticeably reduced by doubling the number of visits at a site from 8 to 16 (Appendix S2: Figures S1 and S2).

The *Naive* approach consistently overestimated rare species occurrence probability (Figure 2, top row) and probability of detection (Figure 2, middle row) for all scenarios because of false-positive detections contributed from a common species. These parameter estimates translated to an “always-present” decision for every site. The severe bias in parameter estimation using the *Naive* occupancy model suggested its application for assessing rare bat species presence requires caution and justification that no false positives occur.

MLESite versus Remove or 2SppCt model performance for determining local species presence

We present our investigation into whether the threshold value specified in the decision rule influenced the median

proportion of sites assigned the correct state of rare species present or absent in Appendix S2. We used cutoff values that balanced the correct versus incorrect decision rates regarding species presence or absence at a site in the comparisons we highlight (Figure 3). The *MLESite* decision rule for species presence was p value < 0.10 and for species absence was p value > 0.10 at a site. The posterior probabilities from *2SppCt* and *Remove* were used with a threshold specific to the desired decision of species presence or absence: decision rule of $\Pr(Z = 1|y) > 0.75$ for species absence (protecting against an erroneous determination of species presence) and a decision rule of $\Pr(Z = 1|y) > 0.25$ for species presence (protecting against an erroneous determination of species absence) at a site.

Regardless of the assumed occurrence and relative activity for the rare species in our simulations, the *2SppCt* model outperformed the *MLESite* approach for correctly determining a species was present at a site (Figure 3, top left panel). The *2SppCt* model median correct decision rate for presence increased from 0.78 to 1 as the occurrence probability increased from 0.25 to 0.50, and the variability in correct decision rates decreased. The *MLESite* median correct decision rate for presence

FIGURE 3 Comparison of decision error rates for deciding rare species presence or absence fitting the count detection model (labeled as *2SppCt* darker green boxes), *Remove* occupancy model (labeled as light green *Remove* boxes), or *MLESite* (mustard-colored boxes). For *Remove* and *2SppCt*, the posterior mean of the Z_{it} -state $\text{Prob}(Z_{it} = 1|y) > 0.75$ was used for species absence, and $\text{Prob}(Z_{it} = 1|y) > 0.25$, for species presence at a site i . The threshold values were selected to balance the (in)correct decision rates (see Appendix S2). The *MLESite* used a p value threshold of 0.10 in the decision rule. Each dot represents the conditional proportion of sites with a specific decision given the known true state of species present ($Z = 1$) or absent ($Z = 0$) for each of 50 simulated datasets with 55 sites each. The columns correspond to the true Z state, and each row is the species site-level decision. All scenario results are provided in Appendix S2: Figures S3–S5.

was improved when the assumed average number of recordings increased from 5 to 11 over the entire survey duration (16 nights of recording). However, the median proportion of correct decisions for presence was always less than 0.5 for the *MLESite* (Figure 3, top left panel). The *Remove* approach always returned a decision of species presence, regardless of the data-generating values (Figure 3, top left panel).

Another way to explore the performance for informing local decisions is to consider the median proportion of sites with incorrect decisions of species absent when truly present (Figure 3, bottom left panel; notice bottom panel is essentially a mirror image of the corresponding top panel). The *2SppCt* model consistently had the lowest median incorrect decision rates compared with *MLESite* and *Remove* approach regardless of the assumed relative activity or occurrence probabilities (Figure 3, bottom left panel). Again, the performance for the *2SppCt* model

improved when the assumed occurrence probability for a rare species was 0.50 and the *MLESite* incorrect decision rate was reduced by increasing the expected number of nightly recordings. The *Remove* approach infrequently resulted in a decision of species absence (very few points graphed in Figure 3, bottom left panel).

For all the approaches we explored, the correct decision rates for species absence were less variable with no clear differences related to assumed relative activity or occurrence probabilities (Figure 3, right panels). The *2SppCt* model was equivalent to or better than the *MLESite* approach for determining a rare species was absent at a site with both having median correct decisions $>90\%$ of the time (Figure 3, bottom right panel). The *Remove* had the lowest correct decision rates for species absence (Figure 3, lower right panel).

Both the *2SppCt* and *MLESite* had consistently the lowest median incorrect decision rate for claiming a rare

species was present when truly absent (Figure 3, top right panel). Note the *MLESite* had a median incorrect decision rate of approximately 10%. As expected, the number should be close to the cutoff value or α used to make a decision because the *MLESite* was based on a frequentist hypothesis test. The *Remove* approach had consistently the highest median incorrect decision rate (approximately 25%) regarding local absence because most sites were assigned the incorrect state of rare species presence (Figure 3, top right) due to the bias in the occurrence and detection parameter estimates (Figure 2, top two rows).

DISCUSSION

Our simulation investigation indicated that the multispecies count detection model (in the two-species case) was equivalent to or better than the current USFWS standard for determining local species presence, which opens up possibilities for integrating summertime acoustic datasets within a common statistical inference framework. Below, we outline the key findings for the four approaches (*MLESite*, *2SppCt*, *Remove*, and *Naive*) compared under realistic data-generating scenarios for bat ARU data. Then, based on our simulation findings, we describe future field investigations that, in coordination with statistical method development, could provide huge dividends for bat conservation. We conclude with a discussion on statistical considerations prior to combining datasets from the different summertime acoustic surveys for rare bats and provide suggestions for sound data integration and Bayesian inferences with uncertainty in the future.

We found that applying the MLE-metric at a site level (*MLESite*) had median correct decisions less than 60% for species presence with most scenarios ranging between 20% and 30%, but greater than 85% for species absence (ranging between 80% and 90%). The *MLESite* had reasonable correct decision rates for absence consistent with its intended purpose of null hypothesis testing for species absence (in “MLE”-metric calculation). However, to increase the correct decision rate for species presence requires increasing the threshold value (α) and/or increasing the total number of identified recordings (N) and the expected number of recordings identified to each species ($E[n_k]$ in Equation 1; de Jong et al., 2019). Practically, a larger sample size could result from aggregating recordings over more visits to a site, orienting ultrasonic microphones to reduce interference that hampers recording quality (Loeb et al., 2015, chapter 4), and/or strategic placement of detectors in preferred habitats of the focal species within the project area (e.g., for *M. sodalis* and *M. septentrionalis* upland and riparian forested conditions; Menzel et al., 2001; Silvis et al., 2016). However, data collected using such a preferential sampling

design are no longer representative of a larger collection of sites (statistical population). Although the *MLESite* accounts for observation-level misclassifications, the information output is only a binary decision of species presence or absence and potential sources of meaningful ecological variation and imperfect detection are ignored (Figure 1, gray pathway).

We propose an alternative to *MLESite* is to consider the multispecies count detection model. We found, in the two-species case, that *2SppCt* had equivalent or greater correct claims of rare species presence (median > 75%) or absence (median > 80%) at a site. The count detection model was developed with the same underlying assumptions as *MLESite*, but can be modified and tuned for different applications. For example, variables that characterize differences in recording conditions (e.g., nightly temperature; Gorman et al., 2021) or deployment locations (e.g., near water features, flyway, and interior forest; Ford et al., 2005) can be exploited to adjust inferences appropriately for nightly recording sessions that had no or very few bat calls detected. Depending on the spatiotemporal sampling design underlying an application, additional parameters can be included that model spatial correlation in the probability of occurrence (Equation 2) and/or temporal correlation in relative activity (Equation 3) using Gaussian processes (Gelfand & Schliep, 2016; Wright et al., 2021). Importantly, the count detection model allows for deeper insights into species–environment relationships in both relative bat activity and presence. These estimated associations, when underpinned by a probabilistic survey design, could be used to improve the prediction of rare species occurrence at a site, thereby increasing the utility of bat ARU surveys to fulfill the goals of ecological research and regulatory compliance information needs.

Our findings are consistent with previous work that urges caution in the application of the *Naive* single-species occupancy model for ARU data subject to observation-level false positives introduced during the automated classification process (Chambert, Campbell Grant, et al., 2018). The severe overestimation of occurrence and detection probabilities translated into essentially a conclusion of the rare species always being present because the common species was always available to contribute false-positive detections. We suggest the *Naive* approach should only be considered when the autoclassifier is 100% accurate for all species that emit potentially overlapping echolocation sequences. Even a small source of false-positive detections (<5%) can bias occupancy model parameter estimates and, consequently, lead to an incorrect conclusion that a species is present within an area (Chambert et al., 2015; Miller et al., 2013).

However, applying the MLE-metric at the visit level to “remove” false positives prior to model fitting (i.e., the *Remove* approach) resulted in many sites where the species truly occurred with zero detections. Our findings

that occurrence probabilities were overestimated and detection probabilities severely underestimated were consistent with field-based comparisons of our *Remove* occupancy model with site confirmation false-positive models for *M. septentrionalis* (Rojas et al., 2018). As a simple demonstration of the ramifications, parameter estimation bias can have on site-level decisions; a site with zero detections and the data-generating values we specified in Scenario 1 would have 0.003 posterior probability that a species occurred (Table 1; MacKenzie et al., 2002). However, using the biased average posterior estimates based on the *Remove* model with 16 nights, the probability would be 0.40. An always-present decision is perhaps satisfactory from a conservative conservation standpoint to ensure the minimization of potential “take,” but also may incorrectly attribute habitat associations or correlates to a rare species that might divert or misallocate habitat management and protection efforts. Based on our simulations, relying on the MLE-metric at a visit level as a means to remove false-positive detections was not sufficient for modeling bat acoustic datasets; however, application in real-world conditions with potentially a greater number of identified recordings and a larger bat species pool could present a different perspective.

Our findings suggest the need for follow-up field studies that compare the *MLESite*, *Remove* approach, and the multispecies count detection model for determining species presence or absence using empirical data with a larger species assemblage. In our simulations, we assumed the true classifier accuracy rates were known and constant for all visits and sites. If these assumptions are not met, the parameter estimates for λ and ψ would be biased and decisions based on the *MLESite* and count detection model potentially compromised. Curating local to regional calibration or confirmation datasets that tune the classification probabilities to real-world recording conditions could substantially improve rare species decisions and provide significant cost reductions for studies that employ human experts to verify the assigned species to a recording (autoIDs; see Stratton et al., 2022). Ideally, future work would consider co-locating ARU-based surveys with other field methods (known roosts or mist-netting) that provide near-definitive evidence that a rare species was actually present (e.g., Miller et al., 2015; Rojas et al., 2018). Pairing such short-term field investigations with statistical method development increases the potential for both lines of inquiry to improve conservation decision-making for rare bat populations.

Our simulations demonstrate that the multispecies count detection model holds promise as a cohesive statistical inference framework for leveraging both local and targeted data collection with rangewide probabilistic sampling to inform regional assessments and could reduce uncertainty regarding local species presence. However, prior to integrating empirical datasets that are collected

under different objectives and survey protocols, the potential misalignment in how sites are selected (spatial design), the grain size of a site (spatial resolution), and the guidance on how field data are collected (response design) should be considered thoroughly. For summertime bat acoustic surveys in North America, the main difference between the NABat and USFWS protocols is the definition of a “site” (in *Summer acoustic bat survey guidelines*) because of the different intended objectives. The omnibus NABat program defines a “site” as a 10×10 km grid cell based on average assumed dispersal distances (Loeb et al., 2015). For regulatory project clearance prior to conducting activities within suitable summertime *M. sodalis* and *M. septentrionalis* habitat, a site is defined as a 0.5-km^2 area (USFWS, 2020). The difference in analytical unit should not prevent integrating datasets gathered under the different spatial designs. In fact, a straightforward extension of the count detection model to a multiscale parameterization that estimates an availability parameter and specifies an intermediate latent level for rare species presence/absence at a specific detector location (e.g., Nichols et al., 2008) provides a reasonable statistical inference framework for a combined dataset. The same model would allow for estimating grid-cell-level species occurrence and information from other survey sites and could be leveraged to improve the decisions made at specific locations within a grid cell.

Minimal alterations to the summertime acoustic survey designs are needed to achieve robust data integration of the regulatory survey data within the broader NABat framework. The NABat guidance already suggested having both spatial and temporal replication within a grid cell (Loeb et al., 2015). Therefore, the only potential modification would be to increase the number of nights to be consistent with USFWS guidance for some detector locations. Also, local site selection for which habitats are optimal for detecting sensitive species need not be changed; the information (metadata) characterizing the habitat surrounding the detector location can be included in an integrated model as covariates for relative activity and local availability, thereby adjusting for the preferential detector placement within a grid cell. For example, the putative day-roosting and foraging habitat of *M. septentrionalis* and *M. sodalis* in eastern North America is upland and riparian forested conditions (Gorman et al., 2022). The NABat acoustic survey design suggests selecting different habitat features within a grid cell to maximize the potential for detecting the full suite of species. The practical hurdle is properly measuring and archiving the local habitat in a consistent manner among survey efforts. The NABat community of practice could provide the mechanism for developing consistent and compatible data fields about ARU summertime surveys, and the online data submission portal facilitates the upload

and download of both the design and response data for species assessments (Reichert et al., 2021).

In addition to the follow-up field investigations that we outlined and the clear potential for data integration of summertime acoustic survey data within the multispecies count detection modeling framework, we suggest an opportunity exists to exploit a full Bayesian statistical decision analysis (BDA) for rare species decision-making. A BDA combines the posterior probability that a species was present with a loss or risk function to determine the potential choice (claim species present or claim species absent) that has the lowest expected risk (Williams & Hooten, 2016). A loss function could be developed *with* decision- and policymaker input regarding whether an erroneous claim of species absence or species presence was more detrimental across a suite of stewardship actions and outcomes (Wade, 2000), for example, the economic cost of halting or modifying a forest management action or an infrastructure project due to an incorrect decision of rare species absence versus the potential loss of proceeding and increasing the possible accidental “take” for an endangered species, if the species was truly present. The decision rule for species presence would be based on the decision outcome with the lowest expected risk. However, for some situations, there could be little distinction between the two outcome expected risk values, but the full uncertainty in the data and a clear articulation of the losses provide added transparency in decision-making.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

All data, novel simulation code, and novel model code used in this manuscript are available at <https://zenodo.org/record/6422770> and cited as Banner (2022). Code to fit the Wright et al. (2020) count detection is available at Wright et al. (2019).

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information may be found in the online version of the article at the publisher's website.

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